

THE ROLE OF SH. KHOLMIRZAEV'S WORK IN THE UZBEK STORYTELLING OF THE PERIOD OF INDEPENDENCE.

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Abstract: This article analyzes Shukur Kholmirzayev and his works written during the period of independence. The author's creativity occurs in all components of the work, through a unique artistic interpretation.

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Each creator tries to explore the human heart, psyche, painful points in his work in his own way. For this, the emotional and philosophical observation of the author, the figurativeness of the image and expression, and the level of figurative thinking are of great importance in the writer's approach.

The author's creativity occurs in all components of the work, through a unique artistic interpretation. One of the important aspects of this originality is the fact that the story is based on figurative imagery. Indeed, literary critic N. Rahimjonov noted that "thinking on the basis of symbols, symbols, metaphors and striving for philosophical depth in artistic generalizations is one of the priority features of current literature" found its proof in this work. Figurative imagery is embedded in the "image" of the work as an artistic and logical whole that organizes the elements that make up the story. The story has a philosophical-psychological character according to its ideological-content and formal features. The talented writer Shukur Kholmirzaev, according to the manner of his work, is a writer who tends to express symbolism mainly through images of nature. His story "Freedom" is also a work in which symbols are widely used, various scenes of life are interpreted philosophically and artistically.

Most Sh. of Kholmirzaev's stories are created in a consistent realistic style. At the moment, we can see signs of conditional-symbolic principle in his stories "Freedom", "Bandi Burut", "Blue Lake", and in "If he kills, let the brave kill" we feel the strength of the journalistic spirit.

The story "Freedom" shows the author's originality in character creation and exploration of the hero's psyche through symbolic interpretations.

The image of Kaklik in the story has become an artistic symbol that expresses the conditional-symbolic principle in our current national prose. Kaklik's captivity has a great social meaning in the fact that he, without realizing his own captivity, calls his friends into the vortex of captivity. In the

interpretation of the image of the kaklik, we feel that the Uzbek people have been in the vortex of ideological captivity for many years. It is no secret that it takes years for a person brought up under the influence of certain patterns to realize his identity and remember his history. The writer assigns this philosophical logic to Kaklik. Through the image of Kalik, he calls people to be aware of the situation in our society. In our opinion, the author's ideological goal is reflected in the fact that Mansur, the hero of the work, named Kaklik Hoinbeka. Because this image reflects the basic spiritual image of some people who forgot their nationality, religion, values, even their conscience and conscience, and entered the path of betrayal.

The image of the partridge is depicted so realistically and convincingly that the reader may not even notice that it is a figurative image. The writer used this method when describing the partridge hunt: the partridge's makeup is kept in the cage; he is taken along for the hunt; when the partridge sings, other cuckoos hear his voice and start gathering around him. They do not know that the hunters have set a net. Honaki does not know that the partridge has betrayed his friends, that is, he called them and trapped them.

Mansoor takes the pet partridge hunting and decides to release it from the cage into the wild. This intention of Mansur was born from his desire to fight against injustice in nature as well as in life.

There is a logical connection between the tragedy of Mansur and the image of Kaklik. Mansur is a young man who was unjustly accused and served several years in prison. For this reason, the social basis of the birth of the idea of giving freedom to domestic partridge in his mind is connected with his fate. A bird sitting in a cage for many years had forgotten to fly, even to find its food and eat. As a freed prisoner starts life again, as much as he can fight for his sustenance, the cockroach should have followed the same path in Mansur's eyes. It is felt that this truth was reflected when Mansur sneered at his loved one whom he freed:

"-Did you hear? "You will die of hunger," Mansour scolded the partridge. And laughed hysterically. - Now where is the warm house for you? Huu ... You don't even have a shelter. - Then the madman got tired and looked at the people above him. - Really looks like a prisoner out of prison, huh? He was released. Now he has to find his bread and eat it..., -He fed the bird again.... It is difficult for him to find and eat it". [Vatan, 1994, issue 15.]

In the story, the fate of the rooster is tragic. A partridge who forgot to fly is attacked by a fox. The fact that the fox lures Kaklik into its trap reminds us of fox-like people. A partridge is not afraid of a fox. Because growing up at home, he

was used to the dog in the yard, he did not feel any danger from it. That's why he thinks that the fox is a dog and leads him to it.

The tragic fate of Kaklik has a certain social meaning. By describing this event, the writer managed to express a figurative thought.

When the story "Freedom" was published, it aroused great interest in the literary community. Importantly, there have been objections to the ideological intent of this work. One of the Fergana admirers of the writer's work interpreted the social content given in the example of the image of a cockroach in this way. In "Ozodlik", the idea of preserving beauty in nature and freedom in society is combined in the image of Partridge. Mansur wants to preserve the beauty of nature, he knows the value of freedom. At the moment, he keeps "Honnbeka" in a cage. Mansur to the partridge who hit himself in the cage. "Hey, stupid bird, what, do you miss the frozen caves? "Look at the street, your friends walking in the mountains are also coming to my feet asking for grain," says Pinok without breaking a sweat. These words show the selfish nature of Mansur, of course. However, in front of our readers' eyes, there are those who do not hesitate to sacrifice the freedom of the Motherland and human freedom at the feet of the "mansurs" in exchange for some "humanitarian" assistance - charity. They are not "traitors" of the Motherland. No, they are just slaves of lust. Unsuitable slaves, terrible slaves". From the point of view of this legality of art, understanding that a freed cockroach is vaccinated against a fox as a doubt about our perspective is the result of not feeling the writer's ideological intention.

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